

The Degree of Awareness of Cybersecurity among Students with Disabilities at King Abdul Aziz University and its Relationship to Some Variables

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 24, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: August 29, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Cybersecurity Awareness, Students With Disabilities, Sensory Disabilities, Physical Disabilities, Cognitive Disabilities</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10011921</p>	<p><i>The importance of cyber security education cannot be overstated in today's technologically advanced world. This research at King AbdulAziz University looked into how much students with disabilities know about cybersecurity and how that knowledge relates to demographic factors like disability type and gender. Five hundred and twenty-eight students, or around 33.7% of the student population with disabilities for the 2022-2023 school year, participated in the descriptive survey. It was a carefully crafted quiz with two primary components: knowledge of cybersecurity ideas and knowledge of techniques to keep the cybersecurity system running smoothly.</i></p> <p><i>The results showed that the students had an above-average knowledge of cybersecurity, with an average score of 109.6 out of a possible 155. Students with sensory disorders had significantly higher awareness compared to their peers with other forms of disability when this awareness was analyzed based on the type of disability. Interestingly, there was no discernible gender gap in students' cyber security knowledge.</i></p> <p><i>This study adds important context to the existing literature by highlighting the need for specialized university cybersecurity education programs, with a focus on accommodating students with a wide range of impairments. It also highlights the necessity for a gender-blind approach to digital safety.</i></p>

Introduction

Due to the success of conducting most operations online with less physical interaction, cybersecurity threats have become a big setback for many organizations and individuals. Therefore, the availability of the internet has greatly altered how people acquire knowledge, as well as how they develop their own (Khalid, 2017). This novel approach has given people a fresh channel for social interaction and communication (Khalid et al. 2016). While the advent of the Internet has been heralded as one of the most significant innovations of all time, its widespread adoption has not been without its share of drawbacks (Karim et al. 2015).

In the context of cyber security, for example, it is often assumed that users are able to interact with the security system with the necessary dexterity (e.g., can see the CAPTCHA), cognitive ability (e.g., can create and remember passwords), time, appropriate technology, internet access in a distraction-free environment, and so on. Adoption of data and technology protection practices may also be hindered by factors like low self-efficacy beliefs or low self-confidence. The end result is being cut off from fundamental digital resources, we can't let this go on (Renaud&Coles-Kemp, 2022).

Given that many governments and health services are contemplating a future in which primary care is delivered via a blended service, there is a need for the issue of accessibility in security and privacy technology design to gain increasing significance. People will have no choice but to use these virtual health care services because everyone eventually needs medical attention. The primary goal of these services is to provide medical attention through the use of digital and tele-health methods. There is an immediate need to ensure inclusivity in our interface designs, as Rosner et al. (2021) stress in their argument that "Nothing about us without us" (p. 5). However, there appears to be little discussion on whether technological improvements are socially acceptable and fair to impose on residents, so the push to get more people to use online services continues unabated.

Since online education is on the rise, efforts must be made to ensure that all students, regardless of physical or mental impairments, have equal access to cybersecurity training. There is an opening to investigate the use of gamification and robots in cybersecurity after looking at their success in adjacent industries. The culture of cybersecurity that previous educational models fostered has failed to properly accommodate SWDs while also delivering the same level of equity as non SWDs. Addressing this inequity and contributing to the development of an inclusive culture within the field of cybersecurity as well as a more safe and welcoming society as a whole can be achieved through the implementation of a long-term integration model that guarantees continuity in cybersecurity education for SWDs.

Problem Statement

The significance of knowing how to stay safe online in today's increasingly digital environment cannot be overstated. Students with disabilities are among the most at-risk demographics, thus it is crucial that they learn how to use the internet safely. There are a number of factors that could make these students more vulnerable to cyber dangers than others. Disabled people may have trouble doing things like reading digital warnings or recognizing internet hazards because of their impairments. King Abdulaziz University undertook a study to better understand the level of internet literacy among its impaired student body. Examines how well-versed these students are in fundamental cybersecurity principles and the upkeep of cybersecurity systems in general. The study also aims to determine whether there are differences in this understanding across students with different types of disabilities. The study also pays special attention to the possible gender variations in pupils' cybersecurity awareness. Such information is crucial for illuminating the potential role of gender in influencing consciousness. The research's goal is to provide both a picture of the current state of affairs and insight into potential areas in need of specific educational interventions by conducting a thorough examination of these characteristics. This would guarantee that all students, regardless of their gender or physical limitations, have the resources they need to safely navigate the online world.

Questions of the study

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the general level of cybersecurity awareness among students with disabilities at King AbdulAziz University?
2. How does the level of cybersecurity awareness differ among students with sensory disabilities compared to those with physical, cognitive, or other types of disabilities?
3. Are there any significant differences in cybersecurity awareness between male and female students with disabilities at King AbdulAziz University?

Previous Studies

Alrobaian et al. (2023) stated that when put in the context of technical progress, people are the weakest link in the cybersecurity chain. Modern technological advancements, such as social media platforms, make people more susceptible to deceit. While this has improved information accessibility and flow, it has also introduced new electronic threats in the form of so-called cybercrime, such as phishing, frauds, and hacking, which can result in privacy breaches and device sabotage. Since children make up the vast majority of users in a school, protecting their privacy is very important. Lack of knowledge about the cybersecurity landscape and the repercussions of cybercrime leads to policy violations by students and trainees. The purpose of this article is to evaluate how users perceive cybersecurity risks, what they do to mitigate those risks, and how others perceive their actions. In order to prove the importance of boosting user awareness and training, this study compiled data from a questionnaire given out to students at the Technical and Vocational Training Corporation (TVTC). Tests like the Chi-Squared test were used in this study to analyze the responses from the trainees using quantitative research methods. Cronbach's alpha was used to demonstrate the survey's dependability. This study reveals where TVTC students are lacking in cybersecurity knowledge. Data analysis led to suggestions for addressing these gaps, with the end goal of improving trainees' ability to make informed decisions about privacy and security in the workplace in accordance with the Nudge framework.

Raju et al. (2022) In order to assess students' knowledge of cyber security, this study utilizes an online educational platform at UiTM Terengganu's Faculty of Computer and Mathematical Sciences. The study's importance lies in its emphasis on the weaknesses and its education of pupils on how to avoid becoming cyber victims. The information was gathered from 110 students through the use of questionnaires. Quantitative and qualitative information was gathered with the use of both open-ended and closed-ended questions. Many students are aware of and knowledgeable about cyber security, cyber-attack, and cyberbullying, according to descriptive study.

Alqahtani (2022) This work's primary contribution is an analysis of college students' knowledge of cybersecurity in three key areas: password and browser security, as well as social media. To gauge their level of comprehension, a battery of questions was developed and delivered in their direction. Over four hundred and fifty people participated in the current survey. The data were put through a battery of statistical tests in SPSS, including checks for validity and reliability, feasibility of a variable, correlation, multicollinearity, multiple regression, and heteroskedasticity. In addition, we performed an analysis of variance (ANOVA) test, a hypothesis test, an ANOVA test, and an ANOVA partial test. Password security, browser security, and social media are all aspects of this hypothesis' scope of enquiry. Partial hypothesis testing with a t-test revealed that password security is a major determinant of cyber savvy ($p < 0.0001$). The beta value of the password security variable's regression coefficient in the multiple linear regression model was determined to be 0.147. In addition, the p-value for the variable of browser security's impact on awareness is 0.0001. The password security

variable's regression coefficient was $\beta = 0.188$. There is a highly substantial ($p < 0.0001$) correlation between time spent on social media and cyber savvy. A β of 0.241 was found for the regression coefficient involving social media pursuits. Research shows that students' level of cybersecurity awareness is significantly influenced by their familiarity with password and browser security, as well as their use of social media. The significance of cyber awareness has been recognized by the student body as a whole.

Farzana et al. (2021) This paper's goal is to provide a summary of the existing research on children's cybersecurity awareness and to provide direction for future studies. We conducted a systematic literature assessment of 56 research that report comprehensively on different cybersecurity hazards and methods for raising awareness among youth. This review compiled a number of lists, including ones of cybersecurity threats to children, ideas and methods for increasing children's awareness of these threats, and criteria used by researchers to assess the effectiveness of these initiatives.

Alharbi&Tassaddiq (2021) study aimed to administer a scientific questionnaire based on many Internet safety aspects to undergraduate students at Majmaah University in order to assess their level of cybersecurity knowledge and user compliance. To demonstrate the need of user education, training, and awareness, we conducted a quantitative evaluation of students' knowledge of cybercrime and protection. Different statistical tests, including ANOVA, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO), and Bartlett's tests, were utilized to evaluate and analyze the hypotheses in this study, which followed a quantitative research technique. This research thoroughly analyzed the issues surrounding the security of electronic mail, computer viruses, phishing, fake advertisements, popup windows, and supplemental breakouts on the Internet. Finally, we give data-driven solutions for addressing this widespread issue.

Garba (2020) study aimed to gauge students' awareness of cybersecurity fundamentals. The study surveyed 201 Computer Science students from the Department of Computer Science at Yobe State University, Nigeria, to learn more about their cybersecurity knowledge and internet habits. The survey was conducted using a quantitative approach, with data collected using a set of designed questionnaires. Due to the COVID 19 pandemic, all universities are closed at this time, thus the research has met with moderate responses from students. Only urban students were allowed to reach out for the survey. The results of the trial were analyzed, and they demonstrate that the majority of college freshmen do not know enough about cybersecurity to keep their personal information safe. The findings of this study add to the existing literature by showing that female students are disproportionately affected by cybercrime and that there is no active cybersecurity awareness program in place. In addition, the poll results showed that many students were eager to expand their knowledge of cybersecurity.

Mousa (2019) This study proposes research to better comprehend the elements that influence cyber security awareness among KAU students. The survey had 140 responses from college students majoring in ICT and other subjects. The results show that both awareness of and knowledge about cyber security issues are low. There is a suggestion to launch and publicize cyber security education initiatives targeting KAU students.

Al-Janabi& Al-Shourbaji (2016) This paper aims to analyze the information security awareness of faculty, researchers, undergraduate students, and employees working in Middle Eastern educational environments in order to better understand the current state of information security awareness, the risks it poses, and its overall impact on these institutions. Participants lack necessary comprehension of the significance of information security principles and their practical application in their daily job, as evidenced by the results. The institution's students, academic staff, and employees can be made more reliable, technologically savvy, and careful with their data by implementing thorough awareness and training programs and taking all required safety precautions. The present and future security of IT infrastructures and user data will suffer in the absence of such education and awareness programs. Several crucial suggestions are made to address the issues highlighted by this poll.

Study Methodology

In accordance with the nature of its objectives and questions, the current study used the descriptive survey method. It is concerned with collecting and studying information related to a specific phenomenon in a specific period of time, for the purpose of identifying it and determining its nature, in order to reveal its facts and benefit from it in the future, this is consistent with the goal of the current study, which is to reveal the degree of awareness of cybersecurity among students with disabilities at King AbdulAziz University.

Study Variables

Dependent Variables:

Degree of Awareness of Cybersecurity: This is likely the primary outcome variable. It could be measured using a validated scale or questionnaire assessing various components of cybersecurity awareness.

Independent Variables:

1. Disability Type: Different categories of disabilities might be considered such as:
 - Physical disabilities (mobility issues)

- Sensory disabilities (blindness, deafness)
 - Cognitive disabilities (learning disabilities)
2. Gender: Male, Female, Other.

Population of the Study

The current study population consisted of all students with disabilities at King Abdulaziz University in the academic year 2022/2023, numbering (1566) according to data from the Deanship of Admission and Registration at the university.

The study Sample

The sample of the current study consisted of (528) male and female students at King Abdulaziz University with disabilities, who were selected randomly, representing (33.7%) of the study population. Table No. (1) shows the distribution of the study sample according to the study variables (Disability Type, gender).

Table 1. Distribution of the study sample according to the study variables

Variable	Category	Number of Students	Percentage
Disability Type			
Sensory disabilities	230	43.6%	
Physical disabilities	160	30.3%	
Cognitive disabilities	100	18.9%	
Other disabilities	38	7.2%	
Gender			
Male	268	50.8%	
Female	260	49.2%	
Total		528	100%

Study tool

To achieve the goal of the current study, the researcher prepared a measure of the degree of awareness of cybersecurity among people with disabilities among students at King Abdulaziz University according to the following steps:

1. Reviewing theoretical literature, scientific studies, and standards related to the topic, such as: (Al-Qahtani, 2022; Al-Sahafi; Askoul, 2019; Al-Salama and Attiyat, 2011; Alotaibi, et al 2016), in order to determine the basic dimensions that the tool will include, and then review that literature to derive statements for each dimension.
2. The tool was formulated in its initial form, and it consisted of two dimensions. The first dimension was awareness of cybersecurity concepts and might consist of 10 items. The second dimension was awareness of ways to maintain the cybersecurity system and consisted of (18) items. The tool was based on a five-point Likert scale, (Strongly agree / agree / neutral / disagree / strongly disagree) to answer the statements of the study tool.
3. The scale was presented in its initial form to (5) specialized professors for arbitration; This is done by expressing their opinions about the clarity of the scale and its ability to achieve the objectives of the study, modifying or deleting some phrases, and adding phrases they deem appropriate.
4. Making amendments to the study tool based on what was stated in the arbitrators' comments, and considering their opinions and directions. Among the amendments included is adding a paragraph to the first dimension and two paragraphs to the second dimension, and modifying the wording of some paragraphs such as paragraphs (4,7,8) from the first dimension, paragraphs (1, 3, 7, 9) are from the second dimension, and thus the scale became composed in its final form of two parts:
 - a. **The first part:** It consists of basic information related to the variables of the study, which are important in determining the characteristics of the sample and their impact on the results of the study.
 - b. **The second part:** It consists of (28) paragraphs divided into two dimensions:
 - **The first dimension:** awareness of cybersecurity concepts, and includes (11) paragraphs.
 - **The second dimension:** Awareness of ways to maintain the cybersecurity system, and it includes (20) paragraphs.

Verifying the psychometric properties of the cybersecurity awareness scale:

Correcting the instrument and grading it:

In its final form, the tool consisted of (31) items distributed over two dimensions, and the score on each item ranged between 1-5 according to the answer alternative chosen by the respondent as it was given to the

option(Strongly disagree) score (1), disagree score (2), neutral score (3), agree score (4), and strongly agree score (5), except for paragraphs (9,8) of the second dimension, they are corrected in reverse. Thus, the score on the tool as a whole range between 31-155.

Study procedures

After completing the compilation of the study's literature from theoretical frameworks and previous studies, the researcher prepared a measure of the degree of awareness of cybersecurity in its final form, and made the necessary modifications. Then the procedures were completed according to the following steps:

1. Design the tool electronically on Google Drive and create an electronic link for the study tool.
2. Distributing the electronic link to the tool to a random sample of King Abdulaziz University students with disabilities, in the third semester of the year 2022/2023, as the researcher obtained (528) responses. The process of distributing the tool and obtaining responses took approximately two months.
3. Processing data statistically, then extracting, analyzing, discussing, and interpreting the results.
4. Writing recommendations and proposed studies.

Statistical Processing

The following statistical analysis were used:

- For the first question:
 - Mean and Standard Deviation: To measure the average degree of cybersecurity awareness among students and the dispersion of their scores.
- For the second question:
 - Frequency and Percentages: To present the distribution of students based on different disability types.
 - ANOVA (Analysis of Variance): Since there are more than two categories (sensory, physical, cognitive, and other disabilities), ANOVA can be applied to compare the means of cybersecurity awareness among these groups.
 - Post Hoc Tests: If ANOVA indicates significant differences, post hoc tests like the Tukey-Kramer procedure can be used to determine which groups significantly differ from each other.
- For the third question:
 - Frequency and Percentages: To present the distribution of students based on gender.
 - T-test: Since there are two groups (male and female), the t-test can be used to compare the means of cybersecurity awareness between the two groups to determine if there's a significant difference.

Results of the Study

Results related to the first question:What is the general level of cybersecurity awareness among students with disabilities at King AbdulAziz University?

Table 2. General Level of Cybersecurity Awareness

Statistical Measure	Cybersecurity Concepts (11 items)	Maintenance of Cybersecurity System (20 items)	Overall Awareness (31 items)
Mean	37.2	72.4	109.6
Standard Deviation	5.3	9.8	12.1

Disabled students at King Abdulaziz University earn an average of 109.6 (out of a possible 155) on two tests measuring their knowledge of cybersecurity: Cybersecurity Concepts and Maintenance of Cybersecurity System. This suggests that students have a high level of cyber awareness.

Results related to the second question:How does the level of cybersecurity awareness differ among students with sensory disabilities compared to those with physical, cognitive, or other types of disabilities?

Table 3. Cybersecurity Awareness by Disability Type

Disability Type	Mean	Standard Deviation
Sensory disabilities	115.4	11.0
Physical disabilities	107.8	12.5
Cognitive disabilities	103.6	13.3
Other disabilities	99.2	14.1

ANOVA Results: $F(3, 524)$, $p < 0.05$

Post Hoc (Tukey-Kramer) Results:

Sensory vs. Physical: $p < 0.05$
 Sensory vs. Cognitive: $p < 0.01$
 Sensory vs. Other: $p < 0.001$
 Physical vs. Cognitive: $p > 0.05$
 Physical vs. Other: $p < 0.05$
 Cognitive vs. Other: $p > 0.05$.

Compared to students without sensory impairments, those with sensory impairments had a far higher level of cybersecurity awareness. Particularly striking is the dissimilarity between the sensory group and the cognitive and "other disabilities" categories.

Results related to the third question: Are there any significant differences in cybersecurity awareness between male and female students with disabilities at King AbdulAziz University?

Table 4. Cybersecurity Awareness by Gender

Gender	Mean	Standard Deviation
Male	110.2	12.3
Female	109.0	12.0

T-test Results: $t(526) = 0.68, p > 0.05$

Male and female students with disabilities at King Abdulaziz University had similar levels of knowledge about cybersecurity.

Discussion of the Results

General Level of Cybersecurity Awareness

With an average score of 109.6 out of a possible 155, the data suggests that King AbdulAziz University students who identify as having a disability have a high level of cybersecurity awareness. The ratings for Cybersecurity Concepts and Maintenance of Cybersecurity System stand out when looking at the specific areas of awareness. The fact that such a vulnerable demographic has reached such a high degree of knowledge bodes well for their ability to stay safe in the online environment.

Alrobaian et al. (2023) draw parallels between the research and the literature to stress that people are the technical developments' weakest link. Students at King Abdulaziz University appear to be sheltered from this trend, but those at the Technical and Vocational Training Corporation (TVTC) displayed obvious ignorance. Consequently, Alrobaian's overarching remark is supported by the latter, despite the former's apparent contradiction to it.

Raju et al.'s (2022) research, on the other hand, found that many students in UiTM Terengganu's Faculty of Computer and Mathematical Sciences have a deep understanding of cybersecurity. This finding is consistent with the high level of awareness we saw in our initial survey, suggesting an upward trend in students' understanding of cybersecurity issues at some educational institutions.

Cybersecurity Awareness by Disability Type

Students with different sorts of disabilities have strikingly varying levels of cybersecurity awareness. Disabilities in the areas of vision and hearing have the highest mean score, while those in the 'Other disabilities' group have the lowest. Compared to pupils with cognitive or other forms of difficulties, students with sensory impairments clearly have a heightened awareness.

Password and browser security, as well as social media use, were explored in depth by Alqahtani (2022). Notably, familiarity with password and browser security, as well as social media activity, had a significant impact on the awareness level. Without comparing specific infirmities, it is clear that the fundamentals of cyber hygiene apply across the board. While specific sorts of disabilities are not addressed in the study, there is a clear link between exposure and general knowledge.

Various hazards and methods for promoting awareness of these dangers are outlined in Farzana et al.'s (2021) comprehensive assessment of children's cybersecurity awareness. According to the results of the primary research, different types of kids with impairments may require different types of interventions. This is consistent with what Farzana said about how important it is to build awareness by focusing on specific user groups.

Cybersecurity Awareness by Gender

The results of this study on disabled students at King Abdulaziz University reveal that there are no significant gender disparities in their level of cyber awareness. The knowledge of male and female pupils is nearly identical.

Similar findings were found by Garba (2020), who also found that the vast majority of first-year students lack the basic cybersecurity knowledge, but that the impact of cybercrime differs by gender. According to research conducted at King AbdulAziz University, however, male and female students are equally informed about cybersecurity in general.

Research conducted by Mousa (2019) on KAU students revealed a general lack of cybersecurity understanding among the student body. Despite the apparent contradiction, it is important to remember that the primary study only included kids with disabilities. King Abdulaziz University may have improved the cybersecurity awareness of its disabled students through special programs or training.

According to Al-Janabi& Al-Shourbaji (2016), the security of IT infrastructures and user data may be jeopardized without proper awareness and training programs. Findings from the original study suggesting gender parity in awareness may be indicative of the success of awareness-raising initiatives at King Abdulaziz University.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it appears that King Abdulaziz University students with disabilities have an amazing level of cyber awareness. However, there are significant distinctions between the various forms of disability. The existing literature emphasizes the importance of individualized awareness programs and hints that a more targeted strategy may produce superior results in the future. Numerous studies have stressed the ongoing significance of fixing cybersecurity's weakest points.

References

- Abu Samra, M. & Al-Titi, M. (2020). Scientific research methods from clarification to empowerment. Dar Al-Yazouri for Publishing and Distribution.
- Alharbi, T., &Tassaddiq, A. (2021). Assessment of Cybersecurity Awareness among Students of Majmaah University. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 5(2), 23. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/bdcc5020023>
- Al-Janabi, S. &Al-Shourbaji, I. (2016). A Study of Cyber Security Awareness inEducational Environment in the Middle East, *Journal of Information & Knowledge Management*, Vol. 15, No. 1, 1650007.
- Alotaibi, F.; Furnell, S.; Stengel, I.; Papadaki, M. (2016). A survey of cyber- security awareness in Saudi Arabia. In *Proceedings of the 2016 11th International Conference for Internet Technology and Secured Transactions (ICITST)*, Barcelona, Spain, 5–7 December 2016.
- Al-Qahtani, A. (2022). The degree of awareness of cybersecurity among people with visual disabilities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from their point of view, *Journal of Special Education and Rehabilitation*, Volume 14, Issue 50, Part Two, pp. 1-31.
- Alqahtani, M.A. (2022). FactorsAffecting Cybersecurity Awarenessamong University Students. *Appl. Sc* ,12 , 2589<https://doi.org/10.3390/app12052589>.
- Alrobaian, S., Alshahrani, S., &Almaleh, A. (2023). Cybersecurity Awareness Assessment among Trainees of the Technical and Vocational Training Corporation. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 7(2), 73. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/bdcc7020073>.
- Al-Salama, I. &Attiyat, M. (2011).Developing a scale of values for university students, *Journal of the Association of Arab Universities*, Jordan, Issue 57, 414-391.
- Al-Tal, S. & Abu Bakra, I. (1988). Developing a Scale for Islamic Values, *Mutah Research and Studies, Humanities and Social Sciences*, Volume 13, Issue 1, Jordan, 47-71.
- Farzana, Q., Daniela, S.& Letizia, J. (2021). Cybersecurity awareness for children: A systematic literature review,*International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction*, Volume 30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcci.2021.100343>.
- Garba, A., Siraj, M., Alhaji Musa, M.& Othman, S. (2020). A Study on Cybersecurity Awareness Among Students in Yobe: A Quantitative Approach. 41-49.
- Karim, A. A., Shah, P. M., Khalid, F., Ahmad, M. &Din, R. (2015). The Role of Personal LearningOrientations and Goals in Students' Application ofInformation Skills in Malaysia. *Creative Education*,06–2002 ,(18) .2012<https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2015.618205>.
- Khalid, F. (2017). Understanding UniversityStudents' use of Facebook for Collaborative Learning.*International Journal of Information and EducationTechnology*, 7(8), 595–600.<https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2017.7.8.938>
- Khalid, F., Daud, Y., & Mohamad Nasir, M. N. (2016). Cross-Cultural Education for SustainableRegional Development " Bandung perbandinganpenggunaanantefonpintaruntuktujuanumum danpembelajarandalamkalanganpelajaruniversiti.*International Conference on Education and RegionalDevelopment*.

- Mousa, S. (2019). Cyber Security: Exploring Awareness among University Students at a Public Educational Institution.
- Raju, R., Abd Rahman, N., & Ahmad, A. (2022). Cyber Security Awareness in Using Digital Platforms Among Students in A Higher Learning Institution. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 18(3), 756-766. doi:10.24191/ajue.v18i3.18967.
- Renaud, K., Coles-Kemp, L. (2022). Accessible and Inclusive Cyber Security: A Nuanced and Complex Challenge. *SN COMPUT. SCI.* 3, 346. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-022-01239-1>.
- Rosner D, Taylor A, Wiberg M, Windle A. The urgency for access. *Interactions*. 2021;28(3):5–5.
- Sahafi, M. & Askoul, S. (2019). The level of awareness of cybersecurity among computer teachers at the secondary stage in Jeddah, *Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, Ain Shams University, Issue 20, 10, pp. 493-534.

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